

Climate Counterinsurgency: How Authoritarian Regimes Block Climate Action

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Abstract

COP30 in Brazil ended with petrostates blocking a fossil fuel roadmap supported by over 80 countries—exemplifying how authoritarian regimes deploy a shared playbook of climate counterinsurgency that systematically undermines the information systems, scientific credibility, public priorities, and civic capacities required for effective climate action.

Keywords: Agency, Autocracy, Democracy, Governance, Censorship, Repression, Civil Society, Environmental Politics, Institutions.

Introduction

Under President Lula, Brazil returned to climate leadership by hosting COP30 in Belém after years of systematic environmental dismantling. Between 2019 and 2022, the Bolsonaro government fired scientists who reported surging deforestation, slashed monitoring budgets, and, according to the Associated Press, deliberately withheld deforestation data until after COP26 negotiations concluded. While authoritarian environmentalism is well-documented, we show that regimes do not simply fail to act. They actively degrade the institutional capacities societies require for climate response, a systematic pattern we term climate counterinsurgency. This goes beyond climate denial. It is the systematic and deliberate obstruction of each pathway through which societies learn about problems, form accurate beliefs, set priorities and organise responses.

What happened in Brazil under Bolsonaro illustrates this pattern domestically. What happened at COP30 reveals it operating globally: despite support from over 80 countries for a roadmap to transition away from fossil fuels, petrostates led by Saudi Arabia and Russia blocked its inclusion in the final text. Climate counterinsurgency is a shared playbook for blocking climate action that circulates across authoritarian regimes and accelerates precisely as climate urgency peaks.

The Four-Gate Framework

Social responses often hinge on whether enough people cross key thresholds of shared understanding and behavior [1]. Research in decision science captures these thresholds as four sequential 'gates' that any agent must pass through to respond effectively to a problem [2]: Information (awareness that a problem exists and understanding its basic contours), Belief (acceptance that the information is credible and the causal mechanisms are real), Values (prioritization of the issue as important enough to warrant action given competing concerns), and Means (possession of the capacity, resources, and pathways to respond effectively). Failure at any single gate prevents action entirely (Fig.1).

This framework applies universally, from individual citizens to corporate executives to heads of state. However, shifting from individual to collective action reveals something crucial. For any single person, being blocked at one gate prevents their action entirely. But for authoritarian regimes seeking to prevent societal response, the challenge is different and more demanding: they must block all four gates across the entire population simultaneously. Otherwise, distributed action emerges despite systematic obstruction.

What serves as gates for individuals becomes checkpoints for regimes, obstacles they must continuously patrol to halt collective action. Climate counterinsurgency operates by strategically obstructing each gate. Understanding how obstruction operates at each gate reveals both the coherence of authoritarian climate policy and where it remains vulnerable to resistance.

Fig. 1. The Four-Gate Framework for Social Change. A sequential pathway showing the conditions an agent must satisfy to act meaningfully: **Information** (hearing about the issue), **Belief** (accepting it as real), **Values** (considering it important), and **Means** (having the capacity to respond). At each gate, failure leads to a distinct state: uninformed (dot), denier (cross), occupied (square), or concerned (inverted triangle) but unable to act.

Only those passing all four become architects of change (spiral). The initial "life" threshold marks that action is possible only for those still alive—a one-way boundary. Deceased (double dagger) is an absorbing, irreversible state. Authoritarian strategies obstruct the pathway by blocking information, undermining credibility, reframing priorities, restricting agency, or, in extremis, killing opponents altogether. Sylvain Mazas and Claude Garcia, 2025.

Gate One: Suppressing Information

The crudest form of obstruction targets awareness: prevent people from learning about the problem in the first place. This works not through total censorship but through degradation. Make data harder to find, remove context and analysis, defund the institutions that collect and communicate findings, and gradually erode the information environment.

Brazil under Bolsonaro provides the clearest documentation. In 2019, President Bolsonaro dismissed Ricardo Galvão, director of Brazil's National Institute for Space Research (INPE), after the institute published data showing surging Amazon deforestation. The administration then imposed budget cuts on INPE's monitoring programs and, according to three Cabinet ministers speaking to the Associated Press, deliberately delayed releasing deforestation data until after COP26 negotiations concluded [3]. Far from random environmental negligence, these were the opening moves in what amounts to an authoritarian playbook for blocking climate action.

Since January 2025, according to civil society monitoring and media reports, the United States under the Trump administration has exhibited a comparable pattern. The National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) retired its widely used Billion-Dollar Weather and Climate Disasters database, retaining past entries but halting updates, ended new editorial content on climate.gov after disbanding its content team, and proposed eliminating the Office of Oceanic and Atmospheric Research while reducing overall funding by roughly 25 percent [4, 5]. In late February, the agency also terminated several hundred probationary employees. Most dramatically, in December 2025, the White House announced plans to dismantle the National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR), the country's premier weather and climate research facility. Founded in 1960 and operated by a consortium of 129 North American universities, NCAR has pioneered atmospheric modeling and weather prediction for over six decades. When they don't outright censor information, these measures reconfigure the institutional infrastructure through which climate data are produced and communicated.

Turkey under Erdoğan demonstrates how control over environmental information operates through bureaucratic opacity rather than overt censorship. Independent researchers have documented the government's increasing restrictions on access to forestry and land-use data. China's 2017 Foreign NGO Law severely curtailed international environmental collaboration, constraining organizations that had been pivotal in monitoring local air and water quality [6].

Gate Two: Attacking Credibility

Controlling information is only the first step. Even when climate data circulate, authoritarian regimes work to erode their credibility. This means attacking the messenger rather than the message, amplifying uncertainty, and offering alternative narratives that cast doubt on scientific consensus. The goal is not preventing people from hearing about climate change but ensuring they distrust what they hear [7].

As Hannah Arendt observed, totalitarian systems do not seek converts but people for whom “the distinction between true and false no longer exists.”

In the United States under Trump, climate science has been cast by parts of the political establishment as politically motivated, with genuine scientific uncertainty inflated into fundamental doubt about whether climate change is happening at all. Donald Trump himself called climate change “the greatest con job ever perpetrated on the world” in his address to the United Nations on September 23, 2025 [8]. When announcing plans to dismantle the National Center for Atmospheric Research—the institution described in Gate One—the White House called it “one of the largest sources of climate alarmism in the country.” The strategy is coherent: first attack the credibility of climate science, then use that delegitimization to justify dismantling the institutions that produce it. This does not deny the existence of climate information but systematically undermines its trustworthiness.

In Brazil, Bolsonaro not only suppressed data from INPE but also accused its scientists of fabricating deforestation figures to damage the country's reputation. Environmental research was reframed as foreign interference designed to block Brazilian development. The message: science is politically motivated, economically suspect, and fundamentally untrustworthy. By seeding distrust, regimes ensure that even those who hear about climate change hesitate to believe it.

Gate Three: Reframing Values

Even when people know about climate change and believe it's real, they won't act if they don't prioritize it. Authoritarian obstruction here works by positioning climate action as conflicting with more fundamental values such as jobs, sovereignty, or working-class welfare.

The economic security frame casts climate action as creating job losses, higher energy prices, deindustrialization, and economic decline. This frame proves particularly effective in economies dependent on fossil fuel extraction or heavy industry. The sovereignty frame positions climate agreements as constraining national development, privileging wealthy nations that are already industrialized, and subordinating national interests to foreign agendas [9].

Hungary offers a clear example. Viktor Orbán does not deny climate change, but his government casts EU climate policy as a Brussels agenda that threatens sovereignty and household security. The symbol is the Mátra power plant, running on lignite from nearby pits. Dirty, yes, and formally slated for phase-out under EU rules. Yet the government has kept it alive with subsidies, defending it as vital for "energy sovereignty" and cheap power for Hungarian families. State-aligned media call climate concern an elite Western fixation, while government rhetoric leans on Russian gas and domestic lignite as indispensable for ordinary households. India under Modi provides a parallel illustration. Coal expansion is framed as indispensable to national development and energy sovereignty.

This pattern of value obstruction operated at global scale during COP30 in Belém. Despite support from over 80 countries for a roadmap to transition away from fossil fuels, petrostates led by Saudi Arabia and Russia blocked its inclusion in the final text. China, the world's largest renewable energy investor, joined the blocking coalition. The final decision made no reference to fossil fuels despite clear majority support for addressing them [10].

These frames work because they're not entirely false. Climate action does require economic transition. International climate governance does constrain sovereignty. Poorly designed climate policy can be regressive. The authoritarian innovation is to position these trade-offs as zero-sum: either economic security or climate action, either sovereignty or environmental protection, either working-class welfare or elite environmental priorities. This forecloses the possibility of pathways that deliver both economic development and environmental sustainability.

Gate Four: Undermining Capacity

The final gate is the most direct: deprive people of the means for organizing effective responses. Even when citizens are informed, believe the science, and prioritize climate action, they cannot act if they lack the capacity to do so.

Capacity was undermined at multiple levels within COP30. Indigenous peoples from the Amazon—those most directly affected by climate change and deforestation—found themselves blocked from meaningful participation in formal negotiations. On November 14, approximately 100 members of the Mundurucu Indigenous group blockaded the main entrance to the Blue Zone where official negotiations occurred, demanding recognition of their role in protecting the climate and the forest. Days earlier, Indigenous protesters had breached security barriers in attempts to access negotiating spaces. On November 16, when tens of thousands marched in Belém in what became the first major climate protest at a UN conference since 2021—Egypt, the UAE, and Azerbaijan having banned such demonstrations at the three previous COPs. Those most directly affected by climate change and deforestation were systematically excluded from the spaces where climate decisions were made.

Beyond excluding those most directly affected, COP30 also demonstrated how institutional architecture can prevent even nation-states from acting. Over 80 countries supported a roadmap to transition away from fossil fuels—they possessed the information, accepted the science, and prioritized action. Yet they were prevented from adopting it by a blocking coalition led by Saudi Arabia and Russia. COP's consensus-based decision rules gave effective veto power to petrostates and despite clear majority support, no formal commitment emerged. The Brazilian presidency announced it would develop roadmaps outside the UN process, effectively acknowledging that multilateral climate governance had been paralyzed by actors wielding consensus rules as instruments of obstruction [10]. The pattern demonstrates institutional architecture itself can undermine capacity—not through explicit prohibition, but by structuring decision-making to ensure that those opposed to action can prevent collective response.

These patterns of institutional obstruction—excluding affected communities and blocking collective action through procedural mechanisms—repeat at national scales, where authoritarian regimes systematically undermine the civic capacity required for climate action. Russia's "foreign agent" framework shows this institutional obstruction. Since its passage in 2012, NGOs receiving foreign funding and engaging in broadly defined "political activity" must register as foreign agents.

Environmental NGOs including Ecodefense and Dront were early targets. Over subsequent years, sustained legal, financial, and reputational pressure forced many of the initially designated groups to shut down or drastically scale back their work [11]. In 2023, Russia extended its "foreign agent" designation to WWF Russia, one of the country's most prominent international conservation organizations. The designation immediately triggered operational paralysis: Russian organizations and individuals became reluctant to partner with an entity labeled as serving foreign interests, while WWF's own funding and advocacy activities faced new legal constraints. By June 2023, Russia had effectively banned WWF's operations entirely, forcing the organization to cease activities in the country. This marked a dramatic escalation: WWF had long collaborated with Russian authorities on issues such as tiger conservation and forest protection.

China under Xi Jinping offers a different form of obstruction. The 2017 Foreign NGO Law severely curtailed international collaboration [6], constraining environmental groups that had been pivotal in monitoring local air and water quality. Domestic NGOs can still operate, but only under close state supervision and without foreign funding streams. At the same time, the government highlights selective environmental progress—particularly on urban air pollution—because it bolsters regime legitimacy. Citizens can observe smog declining but cannot build autonomous climate movements.

Defunding enforcement also belongs here. Having environmental laws means little if they're not enforced. Bolsonaro cut environmental protection agency IBAMA's budget by 30% from 2019 to 2020, and biodiversity institute ICMBio's budget by 32.7% over the same period, while environmental agency staff was reduced by 10%. The result: illegal deforestation accelerated even as laws prohibiting it remained on the books.

India under Modi offers another illustration. The arrest of young climate activist Disha Ravi under the Unlawful Activities Prevention Act for circulating a protest toolkit showed how anti-terrorism powers can be redirected toward environmental advocacy.

Even established democracies have borrowed these tactics. On June 21, 2023, the French government under Macron issued a decree dissolving the environmental collective *Soulèvements de la Terre* (Earth Rising) following protests against mega-reservoir construction at Sainte-Soline, justified by accusing the group of "provoking violent acts. While France's independent judiciary ultimately

annulled the dissolution, the attempt itself demonstrates how democratic governments can borrow from the authoritarian playbook—even if institutional safeguards eventually constrain them.

When institutional obstruction proves insufficient, authoritarian regimes may resort to violence (Fig. 1). Environmental defenders globally face criminalization in 20% of cases, physical violence in 18%, and assassinations in 13%—rates that increase significantly when Indigenous people are involved [12]. In Brazil under Bolsonaro, 26 land and environmental defenders were killed in 2021 alone. High-profile cases include indigenous expert Bruno Pereira (removed from his government position after helping disable illegal mines) and British journalist Dom Phillips, both murdered in 2022 while documenting threats to indigenous peoples in the Javari Valley. The Bolsonaro administration's inflammatory rhetoric—calling environmental activists "cancers" and accusing NGOs of setting Amazon fires—created a climate of impunity where few land conflict-related killings resulted in convictions [13].

The Networked Playbook

The obstruction tactics described above appear with striking consistency across diverse political contexts [14]. This is not coincidence. As Anne Applebaum argues in *Autocracy, Inc.*, autocrats increasingly operate as a network—watching one another, noting what succeeds, and adapting tactics to local conditions. These strategies diffuse through observation and emulation rather than through any demonstrable coordination, producing a de facto shared repertoire of obstruction.

When Putin's foreign agent law sharply curtailed Russian environmental NGOs, other leaders took note; similar legislation has since appeared in at least 20 countries [11].

The playbook spreads because leaders choose to use it. Xi Jinping did not need to constrain environmental NGOs the way Putin did, yet his administration adopted parallel tactics through the 2017 Foreign NGO Law, which imposed strict controls on overseas organizations. Orbán did not need to cast EU climate policy as a sovereignty threat, yet he observed how effectively this frame resonates and deployed it.

COP30 demonstrated how this shared playbook produces strategic alliances across different forms of obstruction. Petrostates that deny climate urgency found common cause with nations preoccupied by competing priorities—economic development, energy security, sovereignty concerns. Together, they blocked the 80+ countries seeking to act. In the language of decision archetypes, the Occupied

and the Deniers formed a blocking coalition against the Concerned attempting to become Architects [2]. The obstruction is systematic because autocrats continuously borrow, refine, and redeploy tactics that have proven effective elsewhere—and because these tactics create coalitions that transcend ideological boundaries when blocking climate action serves diverse interests.

The Democracy Imperative

The most sobering implication of this analysis is that effective climate action and authoritarianism are fundamentally incompatible [15]. Not because authoritarian leaders cannot care about climate—some do—but because the institutional architecture of authoritarianism creates systematic obstructions at each gate.

Economist Amartya Sen observed that no substantial famine has ever occurred in a functioning democracy with regular elections, opposition parties, and a free press. Democratic institutions create structural safeguards against catastrophic failure. When information flows freely through independent media and universities, when leaders face accountability through elections, when citizens can organize relief efforts—early warning systems function and corrective action becomes possible.

Famines persist in authoritarian contexts not because autocrats want people to starve, but because autocratic structures systematically block response. Information about food shortages is suppressed. Official explanations go unquestioned. Competing priorities override human welfare. Organized relief efforts face constraints or outright prohibition.

The climate crisis follows the same structural pattern, but on a civilizational scale. Democracy doesn't guarantee climate action, but it defends the institutional capacity to respond. Independent media and universities surface and validate information, pluralism allows competing interpretations, elections force leaders to address public priorities, and civil liberties enable collective organizing. Strip away these safeguards, and authoritarian regimes systematically block response at every stage.

Can autocracies pursue climate policies? China's renewable energy leadership demonstrates they can, and at impressive scale. However, China's climate action follows a distinct logic [16]. Beijing pursues decarbonization when it aligns with economic competitiveness and air quality improvements—both regime legitimacy priorities—while simultaneously constraining environmental civil society and suppressing inconvenient data. Autocratic climate action tends

toward the partial and instrumental: pursued when it serves regime interests, abandoned when it doesn't. Authoritarian institutions struggle to maintain long-term, comprehensive commitment when political winds shift.

This analysis has focused primarily on national-level dynamics, but COP30 revealed that the incompatibility between authoritarian obstruction and climate response extends to international governance. Consensus-based decision rules at the UN climate negotiations effectively grant veto power to any blocking coalition, regardless of size. When petrostates and authoritarian regimes deploy this architectural feature to prevent action—as they did in blocking the fossil fuel roadmap despite support from over 80 countries—multilateral climate governance becomes structurally vulnerable to the same obstruction patterns observed domestically. The four gates operate at the international level just as they do nationally, and institutional architecture can be weaponized to prevent collective response even when clear majorities seek action.

Strategic Implications for COP30 and Beyond

The Lula administration's reversal of authoritarian environmental policies demonstrates that institutional damage can be repaired—but also reveals how quickly those institutions can be dismantled when authoritarian impulses take hold.

Despite incremental progress on adaptation finance, the COP30 failed to address fossil fuel production. Over 80 countries supported developing a transition roadmap, yet petrostates blocked it. This paralysis occurred not at Gates One through Three—countries possessed information, accepted the science, and many prioritized action. The obstruction here operated at Gate Four: institutional architecture prevented collective response even when clear majorities sought it.

The UN climate regime's consensus requirement—designed to ensure legitimacy through universal participation—grants effective veto power to any blocking coalition. When authoritarian regimes exploit this architecture, the multilateral system faces a dilemma: maintain universal participation or enable effective response, but not both simultaneously.

Two responses have emerged. Brazil announced it would develop roadmaps outside UN processes; Colombia and the Netherlands will co-host a 2026 fossil fuel phase-out conference [10]. These sacrifice universality for capacity to act. The alternative is institutional reform—qualified majority voting, differentiated participation rights, or other architectures less vulnerable to obstruction. Both

responses address the same conclusion: when architecture enables systematic obstruction, effective action requires either bypassing vulnerable institutions or transforming them.

Whether through reformed international institutions or strengthened national capacities, understanding climate counterinsurgency changes the strategic landscape. Instead of asking "How do we convince everyone to act?" we must ask "How do we defend information flows in closed societies? How do we build credibility for climate science where propaganda rules? How do we enable distributed action despite centralized control?" The four gates provide the framework for strategy:

Information. Tie climate finance to open environmental data standards. A UNEP–WMO Climate Information Integrity Index could track suppression and reward transparency.

Belief. Defend independent science communication as a global public good. Protected science-freedom zones within international research programs and cross-border journalist fellowships could maintain trust where media control tightens.

Values. Treat civic participation as a condition for legitimacy. Link social protection programs and just-transition plans to inclusive dialogue, aligning welfare and climate goals rather than positioning them as competing.

Means. Extend explicit recognition of civic engagement as climate capacity. Support civic-space trust funds providing legal aid, digital security, and emergency relocation. Embed democracy conditionality within climate finance, rewarding states that preserve freedoms needed for collective action.

Climate advocacy and democracy advocacy are not separate causes. They defend the institutional conditions under which people can learn about problems, form accurate beliefs, prioritize collective welfare, and organize responses. The authoritarian playbook aims to close all four gates at every scale. Just as democracies structurally prevent famines while autocracies enable them, adequate climate response faces structural barriers under sustained authoritarianism—whether through domestic suppression or international obstruction—that partial reforms cannot overcome. Without democratic governance at both national and global levels, we cannot address an existential threat that requires collective action.

Methodological Note

Our aim is not to evaluate the full spectrum of climate policy performance in these countries, but to identify a recurring pattern of institutional obstruction that impedes societal response. This analysis draws on documented cases of institutional obstruction across diverse political contexts: established autocracies (Russia, China), competitive authoritarian regimes (Turkey, India, Hungary), recent democratic backsliding (Brazil 2019-2022), democratic overreach constrained by institutions (France), and current authoritarian tactics in democracies (U.S. 2025). Cases represent patterns identified by international human rights organizations and academic research across at least 20 countries that have adopted foreign agent legislation (10, 13).

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Diversity, equity, ethics, and inclusion: This research examines forms of violence and institutional suppression that fall disproportionately on environmental defenders in the Global South, Indigenous peoples, and civil-society actors working under authoritarian conditions. We acknowledge our responsibility as researchers in relatively protected positions to amplify, not appropriate, these struggles. We also recognize structural constraints within academic systems: this article is written in English, which is not the native language of either author and that shapes how we can express these ideas. One author (P.O.W.) left academia due to the absence of secure positions, a reminder that precarity within academic labor also shapes who is able to pursue research on politically sensitive themes. Climate counterinsurgency targets not only activists in the field but also the institutional conditions—including academic freedom and employment stability—necessary to document, analyze, and resist it.

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